

Proceedings of 8th Transport Research Arena TRA 2020, April 27-30, 2020, Helsinki, Finland

FORESEE: Future proofing strategies FOr resilient transport networks against Extreme Events

Iñaki Beltran-Hernando*^a, J. M. Isoird^a, Bryan Adey^b, Erlinda Biescas-Gorritz^c, Daniel Castro-Fresno^d, Clemente Fuggini^e, Federico Di Gennaro^f, Noemi Jimenez^g, William Hynes^h, Manfred Bogenⁱ, Jose Diez^j

^aFundación Tecnalia Research & Innovation, Astondo Bidea, Edificio 700, Derio 48160, Spain

^bInstitute of Construction and Infrastructure Management, HIL F 25.2, Stefano-Francini-Platz 5, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland

^cTelespazio Vega UK, 350 Capability Green, Luton, Bedfordshire LU1 3LU, United Kingdom

^dGITECO Research Group, University of Cantabria, Avda. de los Castros 44, 39005 Santander, Spain

^eRINA Consulting, angolo, strada 7, Via Gran S. Bernardo, 20089, 20089 Rozzano Milano, Italia

^fAISCAT, Via G. Donizetti 10 – 00198 Roma, Italia

^gCEMOSA, Calle Benaque 9, 29004 Málaga, Spain

^hFuture Analytics Consulting Ltd. 23 Fitzwilliam Square (South) Dublin 2, D02RV08 Ireland

ⁱFraunhofer IAIS Schloss Birlinghoven D-53754 Sankt Augustin, Germany

^jEuropean Road Federation, Place Stéphane 6B, Brussels 1050, Belgium

Abstract

The overall objective of FORESEE, as an H2020 project inside the resilience to extreme events topic (natural, climate change and man-made), is to provide cost effective and reliable tools to improve the resilience of transport infrastructure networks, as the ability to reduce the probability of occurrence, magnitude and/or duration of possible disruptive events that may affect the security and/or the quality of the services provided by infrastructure operators. FORESEE will address through new innovative technologies, methodologies and resilient schemes the effectiveness of resilient measures to improve the ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and/or rapidly recover from a potentially disruptive event.

Keywords: Resilience; Transport infrastructure networks; Safety; Level of service, Extreme events; FORESEE

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +34946430850;
E-mail address: inaki.beltran@tecnalia.com

1. Introduction

Worldwide and in Europe, natural or man-made hazards are strongly impacting on the citizen's safety and generate increasing economic losses year by year. The transport system is particularly sensitive and critical assets are extremely fragile in the face of unanticipated events.

The UN has defined the blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all, to face this challenge, they have defined 17 sustainable development goals for 2030 related to poverty, inequality, climate, environment degradation, prosperity, and peace and justice [1].

The goals "Build resilient infrastructure, promote sustainable industrialization and foster innovation" (Goal 9) and "Make cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable" (Goal 11) remark that the investment in infrastructure is crucial to achieve sustainable development and empowering communities in many countries and that it has long been recognized that growth in productivity and incomes, and improvements in health and education outcomes require investment in infrastructure.

Concerning resilient infrastructures, there are specific targets to develop quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure, including regional and transborder infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all. Beside those targets, the UN wants to facilitate sustainable and resilient infrastructure development in developing countries through enhanced financial, technological and technical support to African countries, least developed countries, landlocked developing countries and small island developing States 18.

The FORESEE project has prioritized the most disruptive hazards impacting on the transportation network, which are Extreme Weather Events (mainly flooding & heavy rainfalls, snow and wind), landslides, earthquakes [2] and Man-made hazards (intentional and accidental), addressing their impact on the transport assets (bridges, tunnels, pavement, slopes, terminals), on the citizens & freight and cascade effects affecting the transport system (mainly road, rail, multimodal and transport hubs).

The FORESEE project aims to provide Infrastructure managers and operators with affordable tools, guidelines and solutions to ensure that transport assets and services function continually and safely against increasing extreme events which are requiring important investments to upgrade them in order to improve its resilience.

2. Concept

Internationally, there is a growing demand to improve the resilience of our critical infrastructure. This is in response to the fact that critical assets are extremely fragile in the face of unanticipated events. In the context of transport infrastructure, operators strive to ensure that transport assets and services continually and safely in the face of a range of existing and emerging hazards. This has led to a specific focus on the concept of resilience and how this can be defined, measured and improved across the transport system.

FORESEE addresses, the incident phase (prior, during and after an event,) and post incident phase through a continuous learning process.

The consortium has identified some of the main needs concerning the challenge of introducing the resilience in transport infrastructure management:

- To increase the understanding of the risk and costs associated with extreme events in order to reduce the uncertainty allowing more reliable and accurate resilience decisions implementation at different time scales and life-cycle infrastructure.
- To increase situation awareness before, during and after extreme events and the knowledge of the benefits from adaptation strategies based on updated existing technological approaches/methodologies and the

development of new innovative solutions.

- The operationalization of resilience policies into operational practice, by translating them into regulatory guidance, programmatic practices and procedures, funding criteria and procurement processes.
- Cost-performance risk assessment approaches and criticality concepts to support wise investments on adaptation measures and infrastructure upgrading.

In order to answer to the previous identified needs, FORESEE proposes the development of an harmonized resilience assessment methodology and an integrated by design Toolkit able to reduce the impact and the consequences for short, medium and long-term events with a systemic perspective consisting of:

- Update of best available methodologies from a performance based approach: event modelling, adaptive solutions and cost-benefit analysis.
- Situational Awareness System based on best available data acquisition system supported by GIS/BIM mapping technologies.
- Innovative technologies: permeable pavements, slope stabilization systems, innovative drainage and culvert designs and engineering of links.
- Guidelines for the adaptation to extreme events (short, medium and long term) put into the routine practice regarding design, construction, operation and maintenance of infrastructure (pre-standardization activities) and continuous learning.

3. Alignment with the Transport infrastructure sector

There is still a general lack of resilience awareness and capability by infrastructure managers and operators, especially with a long-term perspective, mainly due to the inability to monetize resilience for investment decisions. Resilience Schemes are the measures taken to implement or increase resilience in systems, which can be either proactive or reactive [3]. FORESEE directly involves as partners infrastructure managers and operators to ensure the highest impact of the project. Additional end users will be engaged through the case studies. The outcomes will be validated in 6 complementary real cases in Italy, Spain, Germany and Portugal, as described in the following image.

Fig. 1 FORESEE case studies

In order to ensure that the transport infrastructure sector will better understand the costs and benefits associated to resilience investment, the FORESEE project will integrate resilience schemes into infrastructure life-cycle plans and reliable assessment methodologies [4], both types of results validated by end users participating in the consortium or in the Stakeholder Reference Group organized by and for the project.

The identified end users or main target audiences in which FORESEE is focused on generating added value are:

3.1. National Transport Authorities and transport infrastructure operators, by:

- Establishing a science-based preventive maintenance and upgrading strategy for infrastructure management and optimizing maintenance and upgrading investment for resilience.
- Embedding a methodology to monetize resilience in investment decisions.
- Predicting and alerting of potential risk scenarios at different time scales taking into consideration the age, current condition and residual life of transport system components.
- Increasing the understanding of the (direct and indirect) effects of risk scenarios considering cost-performance risk assessment approaches and criticality concepts.
- Recommending the optimal resilience and infrastructure adaptation strategies (as part of a planned maintenance, integrated in existing procedures, including breakthrough technologies and integrated solutions, short and long-term design recommendations).
- Supporting emergency dynamic management plans to ensure citizens safety and rerouting.

3.2. Users and freight, by

- Ensuring safety of EU citizens against extreme events and the implementation of dynamic, safe and efficient contingency plans (including emergency operations and evacuation).
- Implementing Safer and quicker routes by means of well-defined communication tools and travel times based on patterns and current conditions, including incidents, weather and work zones [5].
- Identification of congestion scenarios and incidents (or prediction associated to risk situations, impacts, rerouting, optimization of interventions (travels, localization, dynamic effects)).

4. FORESEE objectives

The overall objective of FORESEE is to provide cost effective and reliable tools to improve resilience of transport infrastructure, as the ability to reduce the magnitude and/or duration of disruptive events. FORESEE will address through new innovative technologies, methodologies and resilient schemes the effectiveness of resilient measures to improve the ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and/or rapidly recover from a potentially disruptive event.

The specific technical and socioeconomical objectives of FORESEE are:

4.1. Technical

- Developing the methodology to define the resilience baseline, based on the target Level of Service (LoS) and Resilience Index₂.
- Developing a data acquisition, collection, integration and management system₂.
- Developing new permeable pavements, slope stabilization-protection systems and sustainable Drainage Systems₂.
- Developing new innovative engineering of links/interconnections based on re-routing strategies and shift to alternative modes₂.
- Developing a Toolkit for Decision Support System (DSS) to provide efficient and reliable resilience schemes based on performance based risk assessment framework, updated modelling & simulation, solutions libraries and cost benefit analysis₂.
- Generating resilient schemes₂.

4.2. Socioeconomic

- Setting up a Stakeholders' Reference Group₂.
- Developing new slope stabilization-protection systems₂.
- Improvement of communication protocols during extreme events₂.

5. Ambition of the project

The introduction of resilience schemes and tools into EU infrastructure management processes is still at a very early stage. Although, there have been studies and projects developing methodologies and certain technologies, there is a clear gap in the form of integrated methodologies and tools that can be integrated in real maintenance

and upgrading processes, and in particular, providing added value to the users (infrastructure managers and operators) in providing reliable data and guidance for decision making to improve resilience and operation in emergency situations.

5.1. Situational awareness and resilience decision support systems

The main challenges in gaining situation assessments are: a) provision of filtered information to the user, b) generation of knowledge from the collected data and information, c) design of a suitable collaborative infrastructure and d) generation of a common understanding of the situation.

FORESEE will provide advanced situation awareness based on machine-learning consisting of:

- **KPIs:** In order to assess how our infrastructure networks will be affected by future extreme events and our ability to restore them, KPIs will be developed. Currently, researchers and organisations are using a myriad of definitions and indicators for the terms of risk and resilience [6]. FORESEE will provide an overview of this definition and indicator landscape and will make a proposal of how the definitions and the indicators should be used.
- **Data Acquisition Technologies (satellite and terrestrial):** FORESEE will demonstrate how structural deformations can be detected from satellite imagery and then combined with in-situ sensor data and virtual physical environments to create a dynamic real-world model of an asset and its surroundings.
- **Satellite data sets for civil engineering,** that can acquire highly regular information regardless of the location, FORESEE will investigate the enormous potential of integrating multiple technologies into a hybrid solution to better characterise and asset using ‘big data’ analytics, combining multiple space techniques, with the wide variety of terrestrial sensors (SHM).
- **Machine Learning and Big Data Analytics:** The State of the Art in using big data analytics in the evaluation of the resilience of transportation networks heavily relies on the data to be aggregated [7]. FORESEE will offer ways of intelligibly processing the Big stream of Data and will offer means of extracting adequate indicators of system performance and an interdependency methodology that will allow for better assessment of the overall vulnerabilities and the proper counter-event measures.

Fig. 24 FORESEE case studies.

- **Multi-Hazard Cross-Modal Risk and Resilience Assessment:** Many existing risk assessment methodologies ignore spatial and temporal correlation between the risks related to multiple objects [8]. FORESEE will provide a risk assessment methodology that will produce directly comparable information on all objects investigated for all types of uncertainties that an infrastructure manager has to consider.
- **Cost-Benefits Assessment:** A range of cost benefit analysis (CBA) tools are focused on the comparison between two transportation alternatives to meet an identified goal [9]. FORESEE will extend the functionality of existing CBA tools to serve as an operational decision support tool.
- **Advanced GIS/BIM mapping systems:** FORESEE will implement an asset failure prediction capability based on SOTA algorithms that can a) map the highest vulnerability areas, b) map the current status and mechanical stability of transport networks, key assets and its routes c) define failure conditions and derive failure risk maps d) highlight the areas of highest socioeconomic consequences through the application

of multi-criteria decision-making methods including psychological and demographic based parameters.

5.2. New materials, Techniques and systems

Focusing on the high impact and high probability events, FORESEE will provide the following specific solutions as follows:

- Permeable asphalt pavements are designed for maintaining high air void contents allowing water infiltration, while providing the necessary bearing capacity and durability. The high air void content enables rainwater infiltration, pollutants filtering and increased skidding resistance and road safety. However, the limited durability for these materials, surface clogging, low shear stress resistance and their relatively short service life, which difficultly exceed 8 to 10 years, have limited their application in roads. FORESEE will provide the use of novel materials and designs to boost both the permeability and mechanical properties of pavements, so that they can improve their resilience to extreme weather and man-made events and/or improve safety.
- Current drainage design techniques are based on rational method with a probability of precipitation for a given return period according to historical records, IDF curves, concentration time, etc [10]. There is significant uncertainty about projected changes in precipitation and therefore the risk of flooding and drainage design parameters. Current drainage design techniques are based on rational methods with a probability of precipitation for a given return period, IDF curves or concentration time. There are uncertainties about precipitation, risk of flooding and drainage design parameters. FORESEE will make use of statistical techniques based on existing data in order to improve the currents calculations for determining flows of water. On the other hand, FORESEE will improve the design of Sustainable Drainage Systems (SDS) [11] for flood-proofing and surface water management.
- Conventional slope stabilization solutions focus on either retaining the ground of mass movements (high strength flexible membranes) or protecting it against erosion phenomena (geosynthetics), but there is a lack of integrated solutions capable of performing both tasks with one kit. FORESEE will provide the use of novel products that combines in one single kit a mass retaining + control erosion membrane in order to ensure the resilience of both infrastructures and traffic to ground movements minimising production & installation costs.
- Innovative Engineering of links and shift transfer: This concept has not been used yet in the design of multihubs and regarding linear corridor neither taking into account man-made and natural extreme events. FORESEE will provide performance based designs concepts for safety routes and areas inside multi-hubs. Planning of hubs for efficiency management of person and freight traffics and operational maintenance for emergency actions will be developed as well as to implement new long corridor solutions to incorporate flexible capacity/usage design alternatives under extreme events.

Fig. 32 FORESEE disruptive events to face.

5.3. Resilience schemes

Focusing on multi-hazard guidelines addressing the life-cycle infrastructure and resilience phases, FORESEE will provide:

- Operational and maintenance plans: It is a common practise for infrastructure maintenance strategies to include both corrective and preventive maintenance, however best practise dictates that much more predictive maintenance strategies ensures higher levels of resilience but also achieves greater value for money, as well as mitigating socio-economic disruption and loss.
FORESEE will provide a) adequate framework to increase factors as important as safety, efficiency or productivity, b) the knowledge necessary to develop accurate predictive models, covering diverse events.
- Design, construction and remediation plans: Current regulations in the field of risk management are mainly oriented to some specific risk such as the flood risk [12].
FORESEE will provide a new approach where other risks will be considered along with their potential combination at the same time. FORESEE will provide a process to determine optimal intervention programs taking into consideration the spatial and temporal proximity of objects to each other, as well as their ability to provide a specific Level of Service.
- Communication and contingency plans: they are currently defined as static protocols or action to be done as a function of the level of alert and threat typology. Current approaches do not take into account the dynamics of the threat as well as the users' evacuation in risk scenarios.
FORESEE will incorporate the benefits of moving to "dynamic" approaches in which the time-dependent evolution of the people and threat will be considered. Advanced flow simulation and threat modelling techniques for optimizing emergency protocols and communication strategies will be used.

5.4. Psychological and behavioural dimensions of safety from the perspective of users

There is a large body of research on risk perception for a range of situations suffering from a key weakness in that it relies on rational decision-making paradigms such as "willingness to pay" or conscious trade-offs.

FORESEE will explore risk perception and decision-making in a way that can capture non-rational, automatic and emotional influences as well as more conscious economic influences as well as to assess attitudes to transport risks allowing developing a more detailed account of the multiple influences on perceptions of risk and, subsequently, travelling behaviour. Results will be considered in the update of existing tools to facing the problem under a more holistic way.

6. The FORESEE consortium

The FORESEE project brings together a comprehensive, experienced and multi-disciplinary team with a highly diverse expertise and skills set. FORESEE consortium is formed by 18 partners, from 7 European Union countries and one Associated Country (Switzerland). It is formed by all main type of institutions needed to cover the overall value chain of the project, to guarantee project completion and exploitation:

- Research Organisations (TEC, FRA, UC, BATH, ETH, UEDIN).
- High-tech SMEs (FAC, CEM, ICC, IVE).
- Large organisations (RINA-C, FERR, LB, TVUK).
- Concessionary companies and operators as end users (IP, AIS, ASPI) for demonstration of project results.

The multi-faceted nature of the project Consortium creates a strong platform on which to successfully develop a holistic, integrated and commercially viable concept for security and resilience of critical infrastructure which can be adopted and applied by a wide range of end-users.

Due to the profile of each partner, they have been mostly focused into specific issues, thus avoiding replication of work and inefficacy caused by small contributions. There are two levels of partners: technological experts and owner, concessionary companies and operators.

The consortium has been identified to ensure the two main targets: technical and scientific excellence and industrial commitment to ensure exploitation and the coverage of the value chain. FORESEE involves European and worldwide leaders infrastructure management and operation (ASPI, FERR and IP); Large engineering companies (RINA-C, LB, TVUK and AIS) and specialised SMEs of the engineering field (FAC, CEM, ICC and IVE),

complemented by ERF as the federation of the European road industry. Industry participation is represented by 12 out of 18 (66% of the consortia). Leading RTOs in the infrastructure, resilience and social disciplines are represented by TEC, FRA, UC, ETH, BATH and UEDIN.

Together, the Consortium partners bring huge expertise and innovation to all key areas of the FORESEE project, as described next.

- FUNDACIÓN TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION (Spain), whose related expertise is the maintenance of transport infrastructure (inspection, monitoring and solutions); assessment of Climate Change impacts, modelling, vulnerability assessment and adaptation plans and strategies; modelling, vulnerability and mitigation solutions; SHM; simulation of threats and mitigation measures. Its main role in FORESEE is being the Leader and responsible for the coordination and management of the project as a whole; Leader and responsible for the selection of most adequate SHM algorithms. Responsible for the development of operational and maintenance plans.
- RINA CONSULTING SPA (Italy), whose related expertise is Transport Engineering; Asset Integrity Management; Performance Based Design; Technologies and innovative solutions for Structural Health Monitoring; Software Tools. Its main role in FORESEE will be the co-responsibility in the analysis and implementation of innovative engineering of links/interconnections. Co-responsible in the development of the FORESEE Toolkit.
- FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (Germany), whose related expertise is the Modelling of large technical, commercial, security or social systems; Online system control, prediction of future system behavior and investigation of cause and effect dependencies; Modelling, simulation and analysis for Critical Infrastructure Protection, simulation systems and decision support systems; Risk and vulnerability assessment. Its main role in FORESEE will be the coresponsibility in the development of the FORESEE Response, Mitigation and Adaptation Toolkit.
- UNIVERSITY OF CANTABRIA (Spain), whose related expertise is Sustainable drainage urban systems; construction of pavements structures; application of geosynthetics in construction; slope stabilization and sustainable construction; project management and project managements tools; research, knowledge transfer, and training of specialist in the field of fresh and saltwater. Its main role in FORESEE will be to lead the integration of LoS and resilience concept, the development of the GIS risk analysis platform, the development of PA pavements and new slope stabilization-protection systems and finally coordinate as responsible the SP Case Study.
- FUTURE ANALYTICS CONSULTING (Ireland), whose related expertise is the Needs assessment; capacity and operational constraints analysis; Stakeholder engagement; tool development and validation; business model planning; commercialization /exploitation strategy elements. Its main role in FORESEE will be to lead project's Communication and play the Business Innovation Manage role.
- FERROVIAL AGROMAN (Spain), whose related expertise is the Construction and operation of transport infrastructures. Its main role in FORESEE will be to lead Case Study #5 as its responsible
- UNIVERSITY OF BATH (UK), whose related expertise is the Environmental psychology. Its Main role in FORESEE will be to study the Psychological and behavioural dimension of safety.
- CEMOSA (SPAIN), whose related expertise is focused in the field of transport infrastructures including feasibility studies, geotechnical studies, infrastructure and facilities designs, project management, work direction, topography, material quality control, technical and environmental site supervision, testing facilities, pathology studies, maintenance assistance. Its main role in FORESEE will be to act as Responsible for the definition of adaptation strategies to SDS, also as responsible for the development of design, construction and remediation plans and aslo for the development of shakemaps.
- LOUIS BERGER (SPAIN), whose related expertise are Consulting services, ranging from the preliminary design and engineering design to construction supervision and construction management phases, including all organization processes. Its main role in FORESEE will be the coresponsibility in the analysis and implementation of innovative engineering of links/interconnections.
- INGENIERÍA Y CONSERVACIÓN CONTRAINCENDIOS (SPAIN), whose related expertise is the Safety and risk assessment analysis; maintenance activities; safety audits; projects development; performance based analysis in transport infrastructures. Its main role in FORESEE will be the development of management and contingency plans
- INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL (PORTUGAL), whose related expertise is Railway network and road network management, their main role in FORESEE will be to lead Case Study #6.

- AISCAT SERVIZI (ITALY), whose related expertise is Added-values services in the fields of road engineering and transport economics. Its main role in FORESEE will be to coordinate the 6 case studies and being responsible for the Case Study #1.
- AUTOSTRADE PER L' ITALIA (ITALIA), whose related expertise is being a road infrastructure operator. Its main role in FORESEE will be to lead Case Study #2.
- EUROPEAN ROAD FEDERATAION (BELGIUM), whose related expertise are the Dissemination and communication activities. Its main role in FORESEE will be to play the Dissemination Manager role.
- EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH (SWITZERLAND), whose related expertise is the Decision making for intervention on infrastructures; Structural Health Monitoring. Main role in FORESEE will be to lead the definition of metrics and targets of LoS and resilience; Responsible of algorithms for the selection of actions
- TELESPAZIO VEGA UK (UK), whose related expertise is the Satellite earth observation data processing and exploitation; development and operation of SHM systems using GNSS and jointly developing BIM. Its main role in FORESEE will be to lead development of the Satellite Acquisition Program and the SHM BIM based SAS platform
- UNIVERSITY OF EDIMBURGH (UK), whose related expertise is Earth Systems and Environmental Science. Its main role in FORESEE is being responsible for the development of the virtual modelling platform for asset failure prediction
-
- EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH (GERMANY), whose related expertise is focused on Track technology; railway operations, rolling stock and technology; transport planning in passenger and freight. Is main role in FORESEE is being the responsible for the DE Case Study#4.

A Stakeholders Reference Group (SRG) has been set up at the beginning of the project to guarantee the accounting for the demands and the acceptance of all end-users. The group will be composed by around 50 experts from different knowledge areas, as for example: Railway owners/operators, Road/motorways owners/operators, Technical evaluation of the diagnosis and prediction of infrastructures, ITS, Users of the transport systems and Experts on transport logistic. During the Kick-off meeting, Jesús Rodríguez Santiago was appointed as the chairman of this group, whose role will be to lead the interaction between the FORESEE consortium and SRG members.

7. FORESEE long-lasting impact

The Kick-off of the FORESEE project was on September 2018 and therefore, at the date of this document, no publishable results can be mentioned, due to the initial development phase in which the project finds itself.

The European transport network was not originally designed to cater for the challenges and disruptive effects posed by current and future scenarios of potential extreme events (e.g. storms, extreme rainfall, extreme temperatures, earthquakes or man-made hazards).

Changes on climatic conditions affect the original infrastructure design specifications. Analyzing specific assets, such as roads, and assessing the impact models produced by climate change, high costs both in CAPEX and OPEX will be required to cope with the potential consequences. Different sources have pointed out the expected increase in design intensities due to climate change can reach up to 80% depending on the region [13]. The EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change estimated the cost of not adapting between €100 to 250 billion, and that every Euro spent on flood protection could save €6 on damage prevention.

The degree to which roads/rail are adapted to climate change varies hugely between Member States and as stated by the National Road Authorities “To maintain safety and mobility, the time has come to implement tools and methodologies developed in national and international projects” [14].

Climate change impacts over infrastructure networks are expected to widen social differences across the EU as the least developed countries have less capacity to face them. Moreover, according to the results form PESETA II project, at EU level and for the 2070-2100 period the following annual impacts due to climate change on transport

infrastructure (compared to the control period) are expected [15]: Additional cost of around € 190 million for asphalt binder upgrade. A cost reduction of € 330 million due to reduced winter damages; additional cost of around € 300 million due to extreme precipitation; additional cost of € 380 million for protecting bridges against scour (€ 540 million in the period 2040-2070); and costs of around € 35 million from speed limits to prevent rail track buckling. However, Europe is not in the position to cope with these additional costs, since in the last years the EU has been suffering from low levels of investment in infrastructure. This is even more challenging if taking into account that transport activity across Europe is expected to continue growing. From 2010 to 2050, it is estimated that passenger transport will grow by about 42%. Freight transport is expected to grow by 60%.

Sumarizing, FORESEE innovations will impact on an increase of the level of resilience of the transport infrastructure. FORESEE estimates positive impacts based on the experience of the infrastructure managers & operators and knowledge provides of the consortium, such as: Improvements of the Return of the investment (6-9%); Reduction of maintenance costs (15-25%); Breakdowns reductions (65-70%); Increase in productivity (25-30%); Downtime reduction (20-30%); and consequently a significant User Safety and satisfaction of the transport system.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to acknowledge the financial support of the European Commission under the H2020 programme, and are grateful to the FORESEE Consortium partners, namely Fundación TECNALIA, RINA CONSULTING SPA., FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V., UNIVERSIDAD OF CANTABRIA, FUTURE ANALYTICS CONSULTING LIMITED, FERROVIAL AGROMAN S.A., UNIVERSITY OF BATH, CENTRO DE ESTUDIOS DE MATERIALES Y CONTROL DE OBRA S.A., LOUIS BERGER SPAIN S.A., INGENIERÍA Y CONSERVACIÓN CONTRAINCENDIOS S.L., INFRAESTRUCTURAS DE PORTUGAL S.A., AISCAT SERVIZI SRL, AUTOSTRADE PER L'ITALIA SPA, EUROPEAN UNION ROAD FEDERATION, EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZURICH, TELESPIAZIO VEGA UK LIMITED, UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH, IVE-INGENIEURGESELLSCHAFT FUR VERKEHRS-UND EISENBAHNWESEN MBH and Jesús Rodríguez as SRG's chairman.

References

- [1] <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>
- [2] CEDR Climate Change Group Omer, Mayada: The resilience of networked infrastructure systems: Analysis and Measurement, World Scientific Publishing Company, 2013, ISBN-13: 978-9814452816.
- [3] Keeping the Country Running: Natural Hazards and Infrastructure. A Guide to improving the resilience of critical infrastructure and essential services.
- [4] IDEA product from FHWA. Registered users could save frequent trips and receive updated information.
- [5] Hackl J., Heitzler M., Lam J.C., Adey B.T., and Humi L. (2017), Development of flood and mudflow events for the spatiotemporal risk assessment of networks 10th World Congress on Water Resources "PantaRhei," Athens, Greece.
- [6] Heitzler, M., Lam, J. C., Hackl, J., Adey, B. T., & Humi, L. (2017). GPU-Accelerated Rendering Methods to Visually Analyze Large-Scale Disaster Simulation Data. *Journal of Geovisualization and Spatial Analysis*, 1(1), 3, doi:10.1007/s41651-017-0004-4.
- [7] Li Z, Yang C, Jin B, et al. Enabling Big Geoscience Data Analytics with a Cloud-Based, MapReduce-Enabled and Service-Oriented Workflow Framework. Gomez-Gesteira M, ed. *PLoS ONE*. 2015;10(3):e0116781. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0116781.
- [8] Heitzler M., Hackl J., Adey B.T., Iosifescu-Enescu I., Lam J.C., Humi L. (2016), A method to visualize the evolution of multiple interacting spatial systems. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, Elsevier.
- [9] Adler et al, 2010; Huijser et al, 2009.
- [10] Ministerio de Fomento, Gobierno de España. Norma 5.2- IC drenaje superficial de la Instrucción de carreteras (2016).
- [11] Woods-Ballard, B., Kellagher, R., Martin, P., Jefferies, C., Bray, R., Shafter, P. The SUDS manual (2007), London.
- [12] EU, Directive (EU) 2007/60/EC "Assessment and management of flood risk".
- [13] Willems, P; Arnbjerg-Nielsen, K.; Olsson, J.; Nguyen, V.T.V. Climate change impact assessment on urban rainfall.
- [14] CEDR report 2016/05 – Acting on Climate Change. Potential Impacts of Climate Change on Railroads, <https://climate.dot.gov/documents/workshop1002/rossetti.pdf>.
- [15] <http://peseta.jrc.ec.europa.eu/transport.html>.